

Altruism as a Predictor of Well-Being Among Indian Youth Volunteers

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Abstract

The aim of this research was to investigate the relationship between altruism and psychological well-being among youth volunteers in India. The study also focused on finding out the predictive power of altruism in promoting psychological well-being among Indian youth volunteers. For this purpose, it was hypothesized that altruism will significantly relate to , and will predict psychological well-being among youth volunteers.

A sample of 100 undergraduate and postgraduate students aged 18 years- 23 years from universities in Uttar Pradesh and Delhi participated in the study. Participants were actively involved in volunteer initiatives such as National Service Scheme (NSS) programs and NGO collaborations. Data was collected using the Self-Report Altruism Scale and Ryff's Psychological Well-being Scale. Pearson's correlation and simple linear regression analyses were conducted. Results revealed a strong positive correlation between altruism and overall psychological well-being ($r = .62, p < .001$). Moreover, Altruism was positively correlated with all six dimensions of well-being. Regression analysis further indicated that altruism significantly predicted psychological well-being, accounting for 38% of the variance.

Keywords

Altruism; Psychological Well-being; Youth Volunteers; Prosocial Behavior.

Introduction

Altruism is commonly defined as voluntary behaviour intended to benefit another, motivated by concern for their welfare rather than personal gain (Batson, 2011). It is differentiated from related constructs such as prosocial behaviour, which includes helping but may also involve extrinsic motivation.

Altruism is not merely a dispositional tendency; it is also reflected in individuals' behaviours and may demonstrate individual differences in social responsibility.

In the cultural roots of India, altruistic ideals are deeply embedded in ethical and spiritual narratives. The principle of seva or selfless service is

central to Indian religious and community traditions and has been widely discussed in socio-cultural literature (Soudi & Aman, 2023; Gupta & Kola, 2024).

A review of the findings suggest that altruism can foster a sense of belonging and reciprocity, thereby buffering against alienation and stress (Mochon et al., 2008).

Psychological well-being (PWB) encompasses both hedonic aspects, such as life satisfaction and happiness, and eudaimonic elements, including autonomy, personal growth, and purpose in life (Ryan & Deci, 2000; Ryff & Keyes, 1995). It can be influenced by individual personality traits, social relationships, and environmental factors.

Objective of study

The research had the following objectives-

1. To find out the relationship between altruism and psychological well-being among Indian youth volunteers.
2. To find out the predictive power of altruism in predicting psychological well-being among Indian youth volunteers.

Review of Literature

Empirical studies show a relationship between altruism and well-being. For instance, Soosai-Nathan (2015) obtained in their research that altruism is a promising pathway for improving psychological well-being. It was further obtained in the study that an increased perceived altruism level was significantly linked to an increased presence of meaning in life, an essential component of well-being.

Khetani & Shah (2024) indicated that engaging in altruistic behaviors was significant for students, as it appeared to contribute to their psychological well-being, thereby fostering a sense of happiness and satisfaction.

Youth development literature further emphasises the role of meaningful engagement—such as volunteering—in cultivating PWB (Damon, 2004).

However, not all studies reflect a simple positive relationship between altruistic behaviours and well-being. For example, Singh & Parashar (2024) in their study investigated the Impact of motivation and psychological distress on Happiness among 211 college students aged 18-24, who volunteered in Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs). Their study obtained that volunteering increases happiness and intrinsic motivation among college students. However, it also noted that volunteering can produce a higher degree of psychological distress. This suggests that a complex relationship exists between the variables, where positive outcomes coexist with potential challenges. The finding that psychological distress also increases in conjunction with happiness, presents a critical nuance, which warrants a deeper exploration.

In addition, the research conducted by Sivakumar & Devi (2024) also obtained mixed findings. They studied 250 college students aged 18-30 in Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India, who were preparing for careers in healthcare and social work. Their statistical analyses demonstrated that the traits of altruism was positively associated with with prosocial behavior and greater compassion satisfaction- a key indicator of emotional well-being. However, the study also obtained a correlation of altruism with burnout

Thus, it can be observed that previous studies do not align on the nature of relationship between altruism and well-being. This research seeks to fill an important gap identified in the current body of literature, and give it direction

Additionally, understanding altruism's impact on youth is essential for enhancing their psychological well-being. By focusing on youth demographic, this study further endeavours to offer insights that can be utilised in designing appropriate interventions to boost youth well-being.

Hypothesis

On the basis of prior research findings, the following hypotheses were formulated:

H1: Among Indian youth volunteers, higher levels of altruism are expected to be positively related to psychological well-being.

H2: Altruism will significantly predict psychological well-being among Indian youth.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative, correlational research design with predictive analysis. This design aided in examining the association between altruism and psychological well-being, as well as in assessing the predictive power of altruism on psychological well-being among youth volunteers in India.

Procedure

After obtaining informed consent from the participants, data were collected from them via both physical and digital questionnaires. Several NGOs, youth volunteer organizations, and university-based volunteer groups were contacted to recruit participants. Anonymity of participants' responses was ensured. Participants completed the Self-Report Altruism Scale and Ryff's Psychological Well-being Scale either in printed form or through a secure online survey link.

Sampling

The sample consisted of a total of 100 students, enrolled in different academic courses at the undergraduate or post graduate level, across different universities and affiliated colleges in the states of Uttar Pradesh, and Delhi, India. The age of the students ranged between 18 years to 23 years. The participants were involved in voluntary service activities like participating in National Service Scheme (NSS) programs, or NGO collaborations- for a minimum of three months. To ensure fair representation, both male and female participants were included in the study.

Tools Used

The following tools were utilized in the study- 1. The Self-Report Altruism Scale (SRAS) developed by Rushton, Chrisjohn, and Fekken (1981) was used to asses altruism among participants. The scale comprises of 20 behavior-based items, that measure the frequency of altruistic acts such as helping strangers, donating to charity and donating blood. Participants respond on a 5 point scale, ranging from Never to Very Often. The scale demonstrates high internal consistency reliability (Cronbach's alpha 0.89,), as well as good construct validity. It also correlates positively with other measures of prosocial behavior and negatively with aggression. 2. Ryff's Psychological Well-being Scale (RPWB):Psychological well-being was assessed using Ryff's Psychological Well-being Scale developed by Ryff (1989). The measure comprises of 42 items, that evaluates six aspects of psychological well-being: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relationships with others, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. Participants indicate their responses on a six-point Likert scale that ranges from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Previous studies have reported that the scale demonstrates strong reliability and validity, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the subscales ranging from 0.86 to 0.93.

Analysis

Pearson's correlation analysis was used to assess the relationship between altruism and psychological well-being(overall and area wise). Furthermore, a simple linear regression analysis was conducted to determine whether altruism could significantly predict psychological well-being.

Result and Discussion

Table 1

Pearson Correlation Between Altruism and Psychological Well-being (N = 100)

Variable	Altruism
Psychological wellbeing	0.62**
Autonomy	0.33**
Environmental mastery	0.37**
Personal growth	0.49**
Positive relations with others	0.54**
Purpose in life	0.60**
Self-acceptance	0.65**

Note:The coefficient of correlation between altruism and psychological well-being was $r = .62$, $p < .001$, which indicates a strong positive correlation.

Table 2

Simple Linear Regression Analysis Predicting Psychological Well-being from Altruism

Predictor	B	β	t	p	R	R SQUARE	F
Altruism	1.45	0.62	7.85	< .001	0.62	0.38	F(1,98)=61.56

Note: $R^2 = 0.38$, indicating that altruism accounts for 38% of the variance in psychological well-being.

Discussion

The findings of the present study indicate a significant positive correlation between altruism and psychological well-being among youth volunteers in India.

Table 1 presents the Pearson correlation coefficients between altruism and psychological well-being along with its six dimensions among the sample of 100 youth volunteers. The results indicate a strong positive and significant relationship between altruism and overall

psychological well-being ($r = .62, p < .001$), indicating that individuals with higher levels of altruistic behaviour tend to report higher levels of psychological well-being, and vice versa.

The findings further reveal that altruism is positively and significantly related to all six dimensions of psychological well-being. The correlations were 0.33 with autonomy, 0.37 with environmental mastery, 0.49 with personal growth, 0.54 with positive relations with others, 0.60 with purpose in life, and 0.65 with self-acceptance. Among these dimensions, the strongest association was observed with self-acceptance, followed by purpose in life and positive relations with others, suggesting that individuals who demonstrate greater concern for others may also experience a stronger sense of self-worth, meaning in life, and more satisfying interpersonal relationships. Overall, the results indicate that altruistic tendencies are consistently associated with higher levels of psychological well-being across multiple dimensions. Therefore, the hypothesis stating that there will be a positive and significant relationship between altruism and psychological well-being among Indian youth is supported and accepted.

This aligns with previous research that has demonstrated the psychological benefits of altruistic behavior. For instance, Post (2005) found that engaging in altruistic acts activates reward centers in the brain, contributing to improved mental health. Similarly, a study by Thoits and Hewitt (2001) demonstrated that individuals who volunteered regularly reported higher life satisfaction and lower depressive symptoms compared to non-volunteers. Another supporting study by Piliavin and Siegl (2007) emphasized that sustained helping behavior enhances a sense of purpose and life satisfaction, which are core components of psychological well-being.

A simple linear regression was also conducted to examine whether altruism predicts psychological well-being. Results (Table 2) indicated that altruism significantly predicted well-being, $F(1, 98) = 61.56, p < .001$, explaining 38% of the variance ($R^2 = .38$). Altruism emerged as a significant positive predictor ($B = 1.45, p < .001$), suggesting that each one-unit increase in altruism score was associated with an approximate 1.45-point increase in psychological well-being. Thus, hypothesis 2 which states that altruism will predict psychological well being in youth volunteers is accepted.

This supports the theoretical framework of eudaimonic well-being, which proposes that living in alignment with virtues such as compassion and altruism leads to a more fulfilling life (Ryan & Deci, 2000). The findings have important implications for youth engagement programs, suggesting that fostering altruistic behavior through volunteerism can be a powerful tool for enhancing psychological health.

Conclusion

The present study sought to examine the relationship between altruism and psychological well-being among Indian youth engaged in voluntary activities. The findings provide robust empirical support for a significant and positive association between altruistic behavior and overall psychological well-being. Altruism demonstrated strong correlations not only with global well-being but also with its six dimensions—autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations with others, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. Notably, altruism emerged as a significant predictor, accounting for a substantial proportion of variance in psychological well-being. These results align with the eudaimonic framework, which posits that well-being is achieved through meaningful engagement, virtuous action, and the realization of one's potential.

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